

CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE FOR INCREASED YIELDS, IMPROVED SOIL HEALTH, AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

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Abstract.

Conservation agriculture (CA) is an agricultural management system gaining traction globally for its potential to achieve a trifecta of benefits: increased crop yields, improved soil health, and enhanced environmental protection. This approach minimizes soil disturbance through reduced tillage practices, promotes crop diversity through rotations and cover crops, and maintains soil cover with crop residues. By fostering a healthy soil ecosystem, CA improves water infiltration and retention, leading to increased water efficiency and potentially higher crop yields. Additionally, reduced tillage minimizes soil erosion, nutrient runoff, and greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to a cleaner environment. This article explores the scientific basis behind CA's effectiveness and its potential to contribute to sustainable agricultural practices that meet the growing demands for food production while safeguarding our planet.

Key words: Conservation agriculture, Soil health, Water Conservation, Climate Change, Biodiversity.

Introduction

Soil is the surface material that covers most land, containing inorganic particles and organic matter and supplying structural support to agricultural plants, being thus their source of nutrients and water. Agriculture today faces a double-sided challenge-on the one hand, the urgent need to provide food to a growing population, and on the other hand, to do so in a sustainable way [1], without compromising the provision of ecosystem services by the soil, such as carbon sequestration, nutrient supply, and water cycle regulation. Sustainable agriculture is a difficult concept to define, since the environmental, social and economic impacts of agriculture are diverse and interact with one another [2]. In general, it can be stated that sustainable crop production systems are those that respect the environment, improve efficiency in the use of resources and promote human well-being [3]. They are those food production practices that integrate ecological, biological, physical and chemical principles, without harming the environment, as opposed to unsuitable agricultural practices [4]. Soil health is

the state of the soil in relation to its potential ability to maintain its biological productiveness, strengthen environmental quality, and foster plant and animal health. Sustainable agriculture can be defined as agriculture that can be practiced in a productive and profitable way without affecting the health of the soil [5]. Figure 1 shows the main functions exerted by soil. Today, soil health is threatened all over the world. Some of the main threats to soil are erosion, compaction, salinization, nutrient depletion, pollution, and/or overgrazing [6]. On the other hand, land degradation and deterioration of soil fertility are two of the main causes of the decline in the agricultural productivity of agroecosystems. The intensification of agriculture deteriorates the soil quality, and its negative effects have increased in the past few decades. The aim of conventional agriculture is to produce the highest possible yield of crops by the application of synthetic products, energy inputs, and a number of other industrial products. Biodiversity, soil fertility, and ecosystem health are compromised under conservation systems (Cárceles et, al., 2022).

Figure 1. Main functions of soil (Adapted from.

Source: <https://www.mdpi.com/2571-8789/6/4/87>

Conservation Agriculture (CA) is a sustainable and environmentally friendly approach to farming that aims to optimize yields while preserving natural resources and promoting long-term soil health. It represents a departure from traditional, intensive farming methods by emphasizing the importance of minimizing soil disturbance, maintaining permanent soil cover, and diversifying crop rotations. The three core principles of Conservation Agriculture are:

1. **Minimal Soil Disturbance (No-Till):** One of the key tenets of Conservation Agriculture is reducing or eliminating conventional tillage practices. Traditional plowing can disrupt the soil structure, lead to erosion, and contribute to the loss of organic matter. Instead, Conservation Agriculture promotes minimal soil disturbance or no-till farming, which

involves leaving the soil largely undisturbed. This helps preserve soil structure, moisture, and the natural habitat for soil organisms.

Figure 2. Minimal Soil Disturbance

Source: <https://fyi.extension.wisc.edu/foxdemofarms/conservation-agriculture/minimal-soil-disturbance-conservation-tillage/>

2. **Permanent Soil Cover:** Keeping the soil covered with crop residues or cover crops is another fundamental principle of Conservation Agriculture. This cover protects the soil from erosion caused by wind and water, helps retain moisture, suppresses weed growth, and provides a habitat for beneficial organisms. Cover crops are often grown in between main crops or during fallow periods to maintain continuous soil cover.

Figure 2. Permanent Soil Cover

Source: <https://dicoagroecologie.fr/en/dictionnaire/permanent-plant-cover/>

3. **Crop Rotation and Diversification:** Conservation Agriculture encourages the practice of rotating crops and diversifying plant species. This helps break pest and disease cycles, improves nutrient cycling, and enhances overall ecosystem resilience. Crop rotation also contributes to maintaining or improving soil fertility by preventing the depletion of specific nutrients.

Figure 3. *Crop Rotation and Diversification*

Source: <https://tracextech.com/5-benefits-of-crop-rotation-for-sustainable-agriculture/>

Benefits of Conservation Agriculture include

- **Soil Health:** By minimizing soil disturbance and maintaining soil cover, Conservation Agriculture promotes the development of a healthy and fertile soil structure. This, in turn, enhances water retention, reduces erosion, and supports the growth of beneficial soil organisms.

Figure 4. *Soil Health*

Source: <https://dutchopeners.com/sustainability-and-soil-health/>

- **Water Conservation:** The use of cover crops and minimal tillage helps retain moisture in the soil, reducing the need for irrigation and making farming more resilient to drought conditions.

Figure 5. Water Conservation

Source: <https://www.istockphoto.com/photos/water-conservation-farming>

- **Biodiversity:** Crop rotation and diversification contribute to increased biodiversity on farms, creating a more robust and balanced ecosystem. This can lead to natural pest control and improved overall farm resilience.

Figure 6. Biodiversity of soil

Source: <https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/resources/highlights/detail/ru/c/1196842/>

- **Climate Change Mitigation:** Conservation Agriculture practices can contribute to mitigating the effects of climate change by sequestering carbon in the soil and reducing greenhouse gas emissions associated with conventional tillage.

While Conservation Agriculture offers numerous benefits, successful implementation requires adaptation to local conditions, farmer education and outreach, and sometimes changes in traditional farming practices. Overall, it represents a holistic and sustainable approach to agriculture that seeks to balance the needs of food production with environmental stewardship.

Key Components of Conservation Agriculture

The options you've provided seem to be related to principles and practices associated with sustainable agriculture and soil conservation. Here's a brief explanation of each:

A. Minimal Soil Disturbance: This refers to the practice of disturbing the soil as little as possible during agricultural activities. It helps to maintain soil structure, reduce erosion, and preserve soil health.

B. Permanent Soil Cover: Keeping the soil covered with vegetation or organic matter at all times helps prevent erosion, retains soil moisture, and provides habitat for beneficial organisms.

C. Crop Rotation and Diversification: Rotating crops and diversifying plant species in a given area can help break pest and disease cycles, improve soil fertility, and reduce the risk of soil degradation.

D. Integrated Weed and Pest Management: This involves using a combination of cultural, biological, and chemical methods to control weeds and pests in a sustainable and environmentally friendly manner, minimizing the reliance on synthetic pesticides.

E. Conservation Tillage Techniques: Conservation tillage involves reducing the intensity of soil tillage or eliminating it altogether. This helps to maintain soil structure, reduce erosion, and conserve moisture.

Soil Health and Conservation Agriculture

Soil health and conservation agriculture are crucial aspects of sustainable farming practices. Let's delve into each subtopic:

A. Soil Fertility Management:

1. Nutrient Cycling:

- Implementing practices that enhance the cycling of nutrients within the soil, such as cover cropping and crop rotation.
- Efficient use of fertilizers to minimize environmental impact and maximize nutrient availability to plants.

2. Precision Agriculture:

- Using technology to apply fertilizers precisely where and when they are needed, optimizing nutrient use efficiency.

3. Green Manure and Cover Crops:

- Incorporating cover crops and green manure to improve soil fertility, prevent erosion, and enhance organic matter content.

4. Crop Residue Management:

- Retaining crop residues on the field to improve soil structure, prevent erosion, and provide organic matter.

B. Organic Matter and Carbon Sequestration:

1. Cover Cropping:

- Planting cover crops to protect the soil from erosion, improve water retention, and contribute organic matter when incorporated into the soil.

2. **Crop Rotation:**

- Rotating crops to diversify the types and amount of organic matter returned to the soil, promoting microbial diversity.

3. **Composting:**

- Recycling organic waste into compost and applying it to fields to improve soil structure, water retention, and nutrient content.

4. **Agroforestry:**

- Integrating trees into agricultural landscapes to enhance carbon sequestration, improve soil structure, and provide additional benefits like windbreaks.

C. **Water Retention and Soil Structure:**

1. **Conservation Tillage:**

- Reducing or eliminating tillage to minimize soil disturbance, improve water retention, and enhance soil structure.

2. **Cover Cropping:**

- As mentioned earlier, cover crops contribute to improved soil structure, preventing compaction and promoting water infiltration.

3. **Contour Plowing:**

- Plowing along the contours of the land to reduce water runoff, prevent soil erosion, and enhance water retention.

4. **Water Management:**

- Implementing efficient irrigation systems to optimize water use and prevent waterlogging or soil compaction.

By integrating these practices, farmers can promote soil health, increase agricultural sustainability, and contribute to the long-term productivity of their land. Conservation agriculture aims to balance the needs of agriculture with environmental stewardship, ensuring that farming remains productive while minimizing negative impacts on the soil and surrounding ecosystems.

Crop Management in Conservation Agriculture

A. **Crop Selection and Rotation:**

1. **Diversified Crop Selection:**

- Conservation agriculture emphasizes the importance of diversifying crops to enhance resilience against pests, diseases, and adverse weather conditions.

- Selecting a variety of crops helps in breaking the pest and disease cycles and improves overall soil health.

2. **Crop Rotation:**

- Rotation of crops is a key strategy in conservation agriculture.
- It involves changing the type of crops planted in a particular field over a defined period.
- Crop rotation helps in nutrient management, reduces soil erosion, and breaks the life cycles of pests and diseases.

3. **Selection Based on Agro-Ecological Zones:**

- Choosing crops based on the specific agro-ecological conditions of a region is crucial.
- Different crops thrive under different environmental conditions, and selecting crops suited to the local climate and soil type enhances productivity.

B. Cover Crops and Green Manure:

1. **Cover Crops:**

- Cover crops are grown primarily to cover and protect the soil rather than for direct harvest.
- They help in preventing soil erosion, improving water retention, and suppressing weed growth.
- Leguminous cover crops also contribute to nitrogen fixation, enriching the soil with this essential nutrient.

2. **Green Manure:**

- Green manure involves growing specific crops that are later incorporated into the soil to improve its fertility.
- Leguminous green manure crops, such as clover or vetch, contribute nitrogen to the soil, enhancing its nutrient content.
- Green manure also helps in weed control and moisture retention.

3. **Mulching:**

- Mulching involves covering the soil with organic or inorganic materials to conserve moisture, control weeds, and regulate soil temperature.
- Mulch helps in preventing soil erosion and creates a favorable microenvironment for soil organisms.

C. Precision Farming Techniques:

1. **Precision Planting:**

- Precision planting involves using technology to precisely place seeds at optimal intervals and depths.
- This ensures efficient use of seeds, uniform plant spacing, and improved crop establishment.

2. Precision Irrigation:

- Utilizing advanced irrigation techniques, such as drip or sprinkler systems, helps in delivering water precisely to the root zone.
- Precision irrigation reduces water wastage and promotes efficient water use.

3. Precision Fertilization:

- Applying fertilizers based on soil nutrient levels and crop requirements is a key aspect of precision farming.
- This prevents over-fertilization, reduces nutrient runoff, and minimizes environmental impact.

4. Data-Driven Decision Making:

- Precision farming relies on data from various sources, including sensors, satellites, and farm management software.
- Farmers can make informed decisions about planting, irrigation, and fertilization based on real-time data, optimizing resource use.

5. Integrated Pest Management (IPM):

- Precision farming integrates IPM strategies, using data to monitor pest populations and implement targeted control measures.
- This reduces the reliance on chemical pesticides and promotes sustainable pest management.

Advantages of Conservation Agriculture

Conservation agriculture is a farming system that promotes minimal soil disturbance (i.e., no-till), maintaining permanent soil cover, and diversifying plant species. It improves biodiversity and natural biological processes above and below the earth's surface, helping to improve water and nutrient use efficiency and improve and sustain crop production (Conservation Agriculture. Available online).

Region	CA Cropland Area 2008/2009	CA Cropland Area 2013/2014	CA Cropland Area 2015/2016	CA Cropland Area 2018/2019	Percent Change in CA Area Since	Percent Change in CA Area Since	Percent Change in CA Area Since	Percent Change in CA Area Since

					2015/ 2016	2013/ 2014	2008/ 2009	Region 2018/ 2019
S and C Amer ica	49,564. 10	66,377. 00	69,895. 00	82,996. 18	18.7	25.0	67.5	68.7
North Amer ica	40,003. 80	66,377. 00	63,181. 00	65,937. 22	4.4	22.2	64.8	33.6
Austr alia and New Zeala nd	12,162. 00	17,857. 00	22,665. 00	23,293. 00	2.8	30.4	91.5	74.0
Russi a and Ukrai ne	100.00	5200.0 0	5700.0 0	6900.0 0	21.1	32.7	6800.0	4.5
Euro pe	100.00	2075.9 7	3558.2 0	5601.5 3	57.4	169.8	259.0	5.2
Asia	2630.0 0	2075.9 7	13,930. 20	17,529. 02	25.8	70.4	566.5	3.6
Afcik a	485.23	993.44	1509.2 4	3143.0 9	108.3	216.4	547.8	1.1
Total	106,50 5.23	156,75 9.06	180,43 8.64	205,40 0.04	13.8	31.0	92.9	14.7

Table 1. Global spread of CA cropland area ('000 ha) in different regions for 2008/2009, 2014/2015, and 2018/2019, and corresponding percent change

Agricultural conservation, strategies of limited mechanical soil disturbance, covering soil surfaces with organic residues, and diversifying crop rotations significantly affect soil physical, chemical, and biological properties. Nutrient supply capacity, nutrient release cycles and their balanced distribution in the soil depend primarily on the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil, which can be altered by conservation practices and thus affect soil fertility (Himanshu Verma 2021).

Figure 7. Conservation Agriculture

Source: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/news/handling-soil-with-care-conservation-agricultures-role-in-post-2020-cap/>

Conservation agriculture systems

The FAO of the United Nations defines CA systems as an “approach to managing agroecosystems for improved and sustained productivity, increased profits and food security while preserving and enhancing the resource base and the environment (<http://www.fao.org/ag/ca/1a.html>)”. CA has three linked principles (Figure 1), that underpin additional complementary technologies, namely

- Minimum mechanical soil disturbance
- Preservation of residues that provide permanent soil cover
- Diversification of crop rotations and soil biology

The FAO further describes CA as widely applicable to most agricultural landscapes and land uses with locally adapted practices [78, 82–85]. CA is more than avoidance of tillage, – it is an ecosystem approach that involves progressive system-wide change in the farmer’s cultural practices along with a change in mindset, to bypass the use of the plow. In addition, as presented later, CA is C-based and C-focused and an ever-evolving, integrative approach that manages C flows to sustain manifold ecosystem functions, including the efficient production of food, feed and fibre over the long term. The use of cover crops between main crops is a means for generating residues and for adding diversity in CA systems. The early history of cover crops begins with their introduction in the Chou dynasty in China, circa 1134–247 B.C. [86]. Their use has been a component mainstay of most animal-traction based agriculture over the last two millennia. The role of cover crops in CA systems cannot be overstated. In tropical systems, Brazilian CA scientists and farmers have been leaders, providing in-depth study

and practice in cover crop use and production system resilience through increased biodiversity [87]. Because adequate SOM is fundamental for CA success, cover crops are often an important key component. Plant growth must be vigorous to build biomass for soil regeneration and for crop productivity. The strategic use of nutritional inputs and water control become pivotal. While many inputs and energy-use are lower compared to high input mechanized production, CA is not promoted as a low-input solution. CA is however, part of the FAO mantra Save and Grow [61], by promoting optimization of inputs along with assimilation of IPM (Mitchell et.al.,2018).

Figure 8. The three linked principles of CA. Adapted with permission from K. Sayre. Source: Mitchell, Reicosky, Kueneman, Fisher, Beck 2018

The most recent definition of CA by the FAO is found as [2]: “Conservation Agriculture is a farming system that promotes minimum soil disturbance (i.e., no tillage), maintenance of a permanent soil cover, and diversification of plant species. It enhances biodiversity and natural biological processes above and below the ground surface, which contribute to increased water and nutrient use efficiency and to improved and sustained crop production”. The three principles (pillars) of CA are defined as:

- ❖ Minimum mechanical soil disturbance (i.e., no-tillage and direct seeding) through direct seed and/or fertilizer placement;
- ❖ permanent soil organic cover (at least 30 percent) with crop residues and/or cover crops; and

❖ species diversification through varied crop sequences and associations involving at least three different crops.

Four overarching quotations from the Declaration of Madrid declaration are as follows:

I Develop compensatory support mechanisms for the environmental services, which CA provides.

II The promotion of alternatives to overgrazing and the inclusion of rotations with high quality pastures in CA project plans.

III This technique being covered by the terms direct drilling, zero tillage, no-tillage, and no-till.

IV This Congress calls upon politicians, international institutions, environmentalists, farmers, private industry, and society as a whole, to recognize that the conservation of natural resources is the co-responsibility past, present and future of all sectors of society in the proportion that they consume products resulting from the exploitation of these resources. Furthermore, it calls upon society, through these stakeholders, to conceive and enact appropriate long-term strategies for CA and to support, further develop and embrace its concepts. They are the most appropriate means of ensuring the continuity of the land's ongoing capacities to yield food, other agricultural products, water, and environmental benefits in perpetuity. It follows that those environmental benefits provided by farmers practicing CA should be recognized and recompensed by society (Landers et. al., 2021).

Conclusion

Conservation agriculture offers a compelling path towards a more sustainable future for agriculture. By minimizing soil disturbance, promoting crop diversity, and keeping the soil covered, CA fosters a healthier and more resilient soil ecosystem. This translates to increased crop yields, improved soil health with enhanced water retention and fertility, and reduced environmental impact through minimized erosion, runoff, and greenhouse gas emissions. As we strive to meet the growing demands for food production while safeguarding our environment, CA presents a powerful set of practices for achieving a truly sustainable agricultural system.

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